

Manuscript Details

Manuscript number	YSCBI_2018_68
Title	CircRNAs and cancer: biomarkers and master regulators
Article type	Review Article

Abstract

Circular RNAs (circRNAs) are a novel class of non-coding RNAs that despite being relatively abundant have only recently begun to be explored. There are many thousands of genes that appear capable of producing circRNAs, however the function of all but a handful remain to be determined. What is emerging about these highly conserved molecules is that they play important roles in biology and cancer biology in particular. The primary modus operandi of circRNAs are as master regulators of gene expression that sequester or 'sponge' other gene expression regulators in particular miRNAs in addition to RNA-binding proteins. They also function via direct modulation of transcription, and by interfering with splicing mechanisms. Although generally expressed in low abundance when compared to their linear counterparts, they often are expressed in a tissue- and developmental stage- specific manner. Coupled with their remarkable resistance to RNase activity due to a covalently closed cyclic structure, circRNAs show great promise as novel biomarkers of cancer and other diseases. In this review we consider the current state of knowledge regarding these molecules, their synthesis, function, and association with cancer. We will also review some of the challenges that remain to be resolved if this emerging class of RNAs are really to become useful in the clinic.

Keywords circRNA; biomarkers; liquid biopsies; non-coding RNA

Corresponding Author Charles Lawrie

Corresponding Author's Institution Biodonostia Research Institute

Order of Authors Esther Arnaiz, Carla Solé, Lorea Manterola, Leire Iparraguirre, David Otaegui, Charles Lawrie

Submission Files Included in this PDF

File Name [File Type]

cover letter.docx [Cover Letter]

circRNA review (Lawrie).docx [Manuscript File]

conflict of interest statement.docx [Conflict of Interest]

To view all the submission files, including those not included in the PDF, click on the manuscript title on your EVISE Homepage, then click 'Download zip file'.

CircRNAs and cancer: biomarkers and master regulators

Esther Arnaiz^a, Carla Sole^a, Lorea Manterola^a, Leire Iparraguirre^b, David Otaegui^b, Charles H. Lawrie^{a,c,d,*}

^aMolecular Oncology group, Biodonostia Research Institute, Paseo Doctor Begiristain, s/n San Sebastián, 20014, Spain

^bMultiple Sclerosis group, Biodonostia Research Institute, Paseo Doctor Begiristain, s/n San Sebastián, 20014, Spain

^cRadcliffe Department of Medicine, University of Oxford, John Radcliffe Hospital, Oxford, OX3 9DU, United Kingdom

^dIKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, María Díaz Haroko Kalea, 3, 48013, Bilbao, Spain

*Corresponding autor at: Biodonostia Research Institute, Paseo Doctor Begiristain, s/n, San Sebastián, 20014, Spain.

Telephone: +34 943 006138

Fax: +34 943 006250

E-mail address: charles.lawrie@biodonostia.org

ABSTRACT

Circular RNAs (circRNAs) are a novel class of non-coding RNAs that despite being relatively abundant have only recently begun to be explored. There are many thousands of genes that appear capable of producing circRNAs, however the function of all but a handful remain to be determined. What is emerging about these highly conserved molecules is that they play important roles in biology and cancer biology in particular. The primary *modus operandi* of circRNAs are as master regulators of gene expression that sequester or 'sponge' other gene expression regulators in particular miRNAs in addition to RNA-binding proteins. They also function via direct modulation of transcription, and by interfering with splicing mechanisms. Although generally expressed in low abundance when compared to their linear counterparts, they often are expressed in a tissue- and developmental stage- specific manner. Coupled with their remarkable resistance to RNase activity due to a covalently closed cyclic structure, circRNAs show great promise as novel biomarkers of cancer and other diseases. In this review we consider the current state of knowledge regarding these molecules, their synthesis, function, and association with cancer. We will also review some of the challenges that remain to be resolved if this emerging class of RNAs are really to become useful in the clinic.

Keywords: circRNA; biomarkers; liquid biopsies; non-coding RNA

1. Introduction

Circular RNAs (circRNAs) are 5' and 3'-end covalently linked RNA moieties, that despite being relatively abundant, have only recently joined the ever-growing list of non-coding RNA species that play previously unappreciated roles in biology [1].

Covalently-linked RNA isoforms were first identified by Sanger and colleagues in 1976 who observed that some RNA plant viruses were unexpectedly resistant to phosphodiesterases [2]. Subsequently, techniques including electron microscopy and sequencing have demonstrated that these and other viruses, such as hepatitis δ virus, contain circular structured RNA genomes [3, 4]. The first evidence for circRNAs in eukaryotes came from Nigro *et al* in 1991 who observed that the human *DCC* gene transcribed four potentially circular RNA transcripts [5]. Not long afterwards a circular isoform of the *ETSI* gene was identified, albeit at low abundance [6]. In contrast, the circular transcript of the *Sry* gene, identified the following year, was found to be the exclusive transcript produced by adult murine testes cells [7]. Subsequently, studies identified further genes that gave rise to circRNA transcripts, including both the human and rat cytochrome P450 genes [8, 9], the human dystrophin gene [10], and the rat *Shbg* gene [9], all of which were described as minor transcripts of their respective genes. In contrast, both the monkey *NCX1* and the *Drosophila mbl* genes appear to produce primarily circRNA isoforms [11] [12]. Besides from circular isoforms of conventional protein-encoding transcripts, the non-coding RNA *ANRIL* [13], the antisense transcript of the *CDR1* gene [14], small nucleolar RNAs (snoRNAs), and RNase P RNA [15] have also been identified in circular forms.

Despite the accumulating evidence for the existence of circRNAs as a novel class of RNA, for many years they were considered to be transcriptional oddities of only limited

biological importance [16] [5]. However, the advent of next generation RNA sequencing (RNAseq) and its increasingly prevalent use has changed this perspective.

The watershed study was carried out by Salzman and colleagues who used RNAseq to look at pediatric acute lymphoblastic leukemia samples, and found that not only were circRNAs abundant in these cells, but they were also frequent in many other tissue types and cells (Salzman, Gawad et al., 2012). This and subsequent studies have observed that not only are circRNAs much more abundant than originally envisaged, indeed in some cases their expression is higher than those of their counterpart linear RNAs [17], but they are also highly evolutionarily conserved [17-19].

In addition to their functional role as master regulators of gene expression (discussed below), perhaps the most interesting feature of circRNAs are their potential as novel biomarkers for cancer and other diseases. As circRNAs lack free 5' or 3' ends they are remarkably resistant to RNases and other exonucleases [20, 21]. As a consequence circRNAs have much a longer half-life (>48 hours) than linear RNA [22]. Furthermore, circRNAs are expressed in a tissue-, cell-type- or developmental-stage- specific manner [23-25]. In this review we will consider the current state of knowledge regarding their synthesis, mode of function, and role under physiological and pathological conditions, in addition to discussing their potential as novel cancer biomarkers. We will also review some of the challenges that remain to be resolved if this emerging class of RNAs are really to become useful in the clinic.

2. CircRNA biogenesis

There are to be several different pathways that can give rise to circRNAs, largely dependent upon the origin of the donor transcript (Fig. 1). CircRNAs can originate from a number of possible sources including exons [17], intronic [26], both exon and intronic [27], or

from intergenic regions [28]. Exonic circRNA are mainly found in the cytoplasm [22], whereas intronic circRNA (intronic or exon-intron) are predominantly localized in the nucleus [23, 29].

The majority of circRNAs are produced in a RNA polymerase II (Pol II)-dependent manner from protein-encoding genes. However unlike linear RNAs they are not produced by the canonical mode of RNA splicing, but instead most circRNAs are generated from back-spliced exons which differs from the canonical splicing of linear RNAs in that an upstream 3' splice donor (splice acceptor) covalently joins a downstream 5' splice site (splice donor) resulting in a closed circular RNA transcript ligated by a 3'-5' phosphodiester bond at the junction site (Fig. 1) [17, 24, 25, 30].

For the majority of exonic and exonic-intronic circRNAs intron-pairing circularisation appears to be the most frequently used mechanism of circularisation (Fig. 1a) [22]. It involves reverse complementary sequences, such as ALU repeats [17], contained within introns that flank the exons to be circularised. These sequences can pair to form RNA duplexes that act to enhance back-splicing and therefore promote circRNA formation [30, 31]. The introns are then either excised in which case exonic circRNAs are produced, or alternatively retained resulting in exon-intron circRNAs. When the flanking introns contain inverted tandem repeats, they are generally long in length [25], relatively short inverted repeats are also able to promote intron base pairing and circRNA formation [32]. However not all intronic tandem repeats can promote circRNA formation and in some cases, the increased stability of the RNA duplex inhibits the circularization process [32].

For the majority of intronic-circRNAs, circularisation involves short specific intronic reverse complementary sequences that pair to promote circularization (Fig. 1b) [29, 32, 33]. These two elements get sufficient close to bind into a lariat-like intermediate, which is cut out by the spliceosome [29]. These, lariats then undergo 3' tail degradation, resulting in the

formation of the final intronic circRNA molecule. The differing mechanisms result in differences in the structure between intronic and exonic circRNAs. Intronic circRNAs are distinguished by the presence of a 2'-5' junction arising from a residue of the original lariat structure, whereas exonic circRNAs have 3'-5' linkage at the splicing branch-point [29].

Alternatively circRNAs can be generated during alternative splicing events [34, 35]. When this occurs snRNPs (small nuclear ribonucleoproteins) assemble sequentially in the pre-mRNA favouring the circularization of a downstream 5' splice site of an exon with an upstream 3' splice site (Fig. 1c). This leads to exon skipping and the formation of a circRNA.

In addition, some *trans*-acting activator RBPs can specifically bind to flanking intron sequences, forming a bridge that brings the splice donor and acceptor sites close enough to promote circRNA formation (Fig. 1d) [34]. This is the case for the RBPs Quaking (QKI), and *muscleblind* (MBL/MBNL1) [36]. In contrast, adenosine deaminase acting on RNA 1 (ADAR1) and ATP-dependent RNA helicase A (RHA or DHX9) play the opposite role [31, 37]. Both of them inhibit circRNA production by binding to their flanking inverted complementary sequences. ADAR1 executes its adenosine-to-inosine (A-to-I) editing process and destabilizes intron base pairing interactions in the double-strand RNA, impairing pre-mRNA looping and consequently circRNA formation (Ivanov et al, 2015). DHX9 mainly binds to ALU elements inhibiting the pairing of these sequences (Aktas et al, 2017).

3. CircRNA function: Master regulators of gene expression

Although the function of the vast majority of circRNAs remains to be determined, those that have been studied appear primarily to function by regulating gene expression either directly, or more commonly, indirectly, through the regulation of other gene expression regulators such as miRNAs or RBPs (Fig. 2).

MiRNAs are a large class of small (~22 nt) non-coding RNAs that bind to complementary sites in the 3'UTR of mRNAs, to inhibit protein translation or to promote mRNA degradation [38]. In common with other competitive endogenous RNAs (ceRNAs), many circRNAs contain miRNA response elements (MRE), and can therefore compete for miRNA binding with their cognate target mRNAs (Fig. 2a) [24, 39, 40]. The strongest evidence for this 'sponge' activity came from studies of the circRNA *ciRS-7* otherwise known as *CDRIas* which contains more than 70 potential binding sites for *miR-7*, and reduced expression of this circRNA resulted in reduced expression of *miR-7* target genes [24, 40]. Similarly, the circular transcript of *SRY* (sex-determining region Y), *circSRY* gene contains 16 binding sites for *miR-138* [41]. It should be noted however, that whilst this mechanism is by far the most intensively studied, the relative importance of this form of regulation remains uncertain as the majority of circRNAs do not contain multiple binding sites for miRNAs [41, 42].

As the majority of circRNAs are derived from protein encoding exons, their expression can affect the splicing of pre-cursor transcripts leading to lower levels of mRNA gene expression and exon skipping (Fig. 2b) [36]. In addition, high levels of circRNA expression can out-compete linear RNA expression again resulting in lower levels of mRNA [22, 43].

Intronic circRNAs can regulate parental gene expression by acting as scaffolds for RBPs and ribosomal RNA that regulate the transcriptional machinery [23, 24, 29, 36] (Fig. 2c). In the case of the MBL protein for example the circular transcript *circMBL* can bind to the parental protein thereby inhibiting further production of the *MBL* transcript in a regulatory feedback loop [36]. Similar regulatory loops have been described for *FOXO3* [44], and the *ANRIL* gene associated with cardiovascular disease [45]. Both intronic and exon-intron circRNAs are mainly localized in the nucleus, where they can additionally, interact with RNA polymerase II complexes to regulate transcription in a *cis*-manner [23, 29].

Nuclear-restricted circRNA such as exon-intronic circRNAs have been shown to regulate transcription by associating with RBPs to prevent nuclear transportation (Fig. 2d) [23, 29]. For example, *circ-Foxo3* binds to FAK and HIF-1 α proteins thereby preventing their nuclear translocation, resulting in a reduction of their anti-senescence and anti-stress functions [44].

Although the majority of circRNAs have been shown not to associate with ribosomes or the translational machinery [41], it has been demonstrated that the presence of an internal ribosome entry site (IRES) in the circRNA sequence would allow it to be translated into protein (*in vitro*) (Fig. 2e) [46]. It was subsequently found that some circRNAs do indeed contain potential translation initiation sites (Jeck & Sharpless, 2014). Recent studies have found that both *circZNF609* and *circMBL* are associated with polysomes in cells [47, 48]. It should be noted however that the levels of circRNAs associated with polysomes is low, and that the function of these peptides remains unknown, although levels of the *circMBL* appear to be elevated under conditions of cellular stress [48].

4. Physiological and pathological functions of circRNAs

Although circRNAs are typically expressed at low levels, the evolutionary conservation and widespread occurrence of this class of RNAs suggests a functional significance that has been borne out by recent research investigating their involvement in both physiological and pathological processes. Before considering the role of circRNAs in disease we should consider their function under physiological conditions.

The role of circRNAs under physiological conditions has been most extensively explored in the brain. Many circRNAs appear to be upregulated during mammalian neuronal differentiation [49] [18] and synaptogenesis [42], as well in *Drosophila* neural cells [36, 50].

The mechanistic explanation to why circRNAs appear to be highly expressed in the brain is unclear although it has been suggested that this phenomenon may result from the preferential post-transcriptional accumulation of circRNA transcripts rather than increased expression levels. Brain-specific circRNAs are highly conserved between human, mouse and *Drosophila* [18, 36], and dysregulation of RBPs involved in circRNA regulation such as TDP-43, Ataxin-1, and *muscleblind* are associated with neurodegenerative disorders [51-53]. Reduced levels of CDR1as/ciRS-7 circRNAs have been reported in Alzheimer's disease patients [54], and *Cdr1as* knockout mice developed a synaptic dysfunction associated with neuropsychiatric disorders [55].

CircRNAs have also been implicated in innate immune response mechanisms, and it has been reported that mammalian HeLa cells containing exogenously produced circRNAs cause a potent induction of genes involved in the cellular response to viral infections [56]. Conversely, expression levels of some circRNAs are regulated by immunological molecules such as NF90/NF110 [57], and hematopoietic stem cells can be protected from autoimmunity cGAS-mediated exhaustion by the circRNA *cia-cGAS* [58].

Blood is another source of highly expressed circRNAs under physiological conditions and in one study over 4000 different circRNAs were identified, many more than that found in either liver or cerebellum [59]. Even higher numbers of circRNAs (>15,000) were identified in human heart tissue [60]. As a consequence of this rich landscape of circRNAs, many studies have examined both the functional role and biomarker potential of these molecules in diseases of the cardiovascular system. The circRNA heart-related circRNA (HRCR) acts as a sponge for *miR-223*, and has been shown to attenuate the pathogenesis of cardiac disease [61]. In cardiac fibrosis, *circRNA-000203* was shown to promote expression of fibrosis related genes by acting as a sponge for *miR-26-5p* [62], and *circRNA-010567* has a similar function through targeting

miR-141 [63]. The circRNA, *ciRS-7* has been implemented in myocardial infarction by acting as sponge for *miR-7* [64].

4.1 circRNAs and cancer

The functional significance of circRNAs in cancer are well documented, and includes the evasion of growth suppressors and cell death, activation of invasion and metastasis, angiogenesis and sustained proliferative signalling. For example, in gastric cancer the circRNA *LARP4* inhibits proliferation and invasion of tumour cells by sponging levels of *miR-424-5p* and its target gene *LATS1* [65]. In hepatocellular carcinoma, the circRNA *MTO1* can suppress growth of tumour cells by acting as a sponge for *miR-9* thereby increasing expression of the target gene *CDKN1A* (p21) [66]. *circRNA100338* was found to play a similar role in hepatitis B-related hepatocellular carcinoma via regulation of *miR-141-3p* [67]. Inhibition of *circZKSCAN1* expression in hepatocellular carcinoma cells resulted in increased levels of proliferation, migration and invasion [68], whilst *CDRIas* was shown to mediate its effect on cell proliferation by regulating expression of *EGFR* by acting as sponge for *miR-7* expression [69]. In bladder cancer, *circTCF25* acts as a sponge for both *miR-107* and *miR-103a-3p* leading to increased levels of CDK6 and the promotion of cells to transit into G1/S phase [70]. In colorectal cancer *circRNA_001569* was found to regulate proliferation and invasion properties of cells by acting as a sponge for *miR-145*, thereby modulating levels of E2F5, BAG4 and FMNL2 proteins resulting G2/M phase arrest and decreased apoptosis levels [71]. In a similar manner *circRNA_0020397* was demonstrated to effect cell viability, invasion properties and apoptosis by acting as a sponge for *miR-138* causing increases in the levels of *TERT* and *PD-L1* [72]. The circRNA transcript of the tumour suppressor gene *ITCH* regulates cell proliferation rates in lung cancer through sponging *miR-7* and *miR-214* [73]. In breast cancer, circRNA

ABCB10 was shown to promote progression and metastasis by functioning as a sponge for *miR-1271* [74], and similarly *circ_001982* through reducing levels of *miR-143* [75]. Finally, modulation of circRNA *DENND4C* resulted in increased levels of tumour cell proliferation under hypoxic conditions [76].

5. CircRNAs as biomarkers

According to the National Cancer Institute a biomarker is defined as “a biological molecule found in blood, other body fluids, or tissues that is a sign of a normal or abnormal process, or of a condition or disease”. An ideal biomarker should have a high specificity, sensitivity and predictive power. Although the field of circRNA is very much its infancy, there are several characteristics of circRNAs that suggest that they could be potentially valuable biomarkers for cancer and other diseases. Firstly, the lack of 5' or 3' ends makes circRNAs highly resistant to RNase activity, [23-25]. Secondly, they are often expressed in a tissue- and developmental-stage specific manner, and thirdly, that they are abundant in various tissues and body fluids including blood, plasma, serum, or even in exosomes, making them ideal candidates as liquid biopsy biomarkers [59, 77].

CircRNAs have been most widely studied as diagnostic biomarkers, although recent studies have extended this to prognostic biomarkers (Table 1). As far as we are aware to date there are no reports of circRNAs as predictive biomarkers. The majority of circRNA biomarker studies have been carried out on tissue biopsies, with only a handful of studies looking at their potential in liquid biopsies (plasma, serum or purified exosomes).

Probably the most studied circRNA biomarker is *ciRS-7*, also known as *CDRIas*, which has been associated with diagnosis and poor prognostic outcome when highly expressed in colorectal [78], gastric [79] oesophageal cancer [80], and hepatocellular carcinoma [81]. In

contrast, low levels of *circ-ITCH* have been associated with diagnosis of colorectal [82], lung [83], oesophageal cancer [84], and hepatocellular carcinoma [85]. Similarly, low levels of *circ-FOXO3* were associated with lung cancer [86], and in breast cancer tissue [87]. In gastric cancer *Circ-PVT1* is up-regulated in tumour tissue resulting in increased levels of cell proliferation through sponging of *miR-125* [88]. In contrast, levels of *circ-002059* were downregulated in the blood of gastric cancer patients [89]. Similarly, levels of *circ-0000190* are also reportedly down-regulated in the gastric cancer tumour tissues and plasma [90]. *Circ-100269* also has reduced expression in patient tissue and *in vitro* was shown to inhibit cell proliferation through sponging *miR-630* [91]. Another study found that levels of four circRNAs (*circ-202308*, *circ-104423*, *circ-104916* and *circ-100269*) were significantly different between prognostic groups [92]. In hepatocellular carcinoma, *circ-0005075* was found to be more highly expressed in tumour than normal tissue [93], where's *circ-0001649* was down-regulated [94]. Interestingly, these circRNAs contain binding sites for *miR-93* and *miR-182* respectively, both previously identified for biomarkers hepatocellular carcinoma [95]. *Circ-0013958* has been found to be up-regulated in both tumour tissue and plasma from lung cancer patients [96], and similarly *circ-100876* is up-regulated in lung cancer tissue and was shown to be associated with poor prognostic indicators [97]. In addition, *circ-404833* and *circ-406483* are also more highly expressed in the tissue of early stage lung cancer patients than control tissues [98].

6. Discussion

The identification of circRNAs that are associated with cancer and other diseases continues to gather pace and the number of publications in the last couple of years demonstrates that this novel class of ncRNA has enormous potential, none more so than their use as cancer biomarkers. However, it should be borne in mind that the vast majority of circRNA biomarker

studies to date are single centre, retrospective and generally underpowered (Table 1). As a consequence, a note of caution should be sounded regarding the robustness of these studies and in reality, very few of the identified circRNAs are likely to make it into clinical practice. Not least of all because the techniques used to identify and validate circRNAs that are largely experimental and approaches remain to be standardised. Besides from variability in regards to the starting material used in experiments (e.g. purification of cells, cell types, control populations, RNA extraction procedures etc.), there is inherent variability in the various platforms used for circRNA discovery and validation.

The major approaches used for circRNA discovery are RNA-seq, and specialist microarray platforms. Although RNA-seq is increasingly prevalent in genomic studies, circRNA sequences are not usually detected as their lack of poly(A) tail precludes their capture in most routine RNAseq library preparation protocols. As a consequence, these studies use modified library preparation protocols including the use of ribosomal RNA depletion, poly(A)-selection and/or RNase R treatment, all of which significantly increase circRNA representation but can also result in variability [99]. In particular care should be taken to avoid potential technical artefacts such as differences in the sensitivity of circRNAs to RNase R treatment [17, 50], differences in size exclusion protocols [25], or the presence of artefactual backsplice sequences wrongly identified as circRNAs that can be generated by template switching by the retrotranscriptase [100-102], rolling circle amplification [103] or the ligation of two distinct cDNAs [104]. The bioinformatic identification of circRNA from RNAseq data is also far from standardised and several algorithms have been developed of distinct alignment methodologies and heuristics, leading to highly divergent results [99, 105, 106].

Microarray-based profiling of circRNAs is also widely used, with circRNAs being detected by their hybridization to probes spanning the backspliced junction sequence. Currently the only commercial microarray platform for circRNA detection is provided by Arraystar

[\(www.arraystar.com/\)](http://www.arraystar.com/), although this platform is not free from controversy since it is not clear to what extent those probes could detect also linear transcripts [107].

So whilst the potential of circRNAs as cancer biomarkers, and even novel therapeutic molecules, is clear, it is equally clear that much has still to be done if these molecules are not to remain another ncRNA oddity, but really to translate their potential to the clinic for the benefit of cancer patients.

Acknowledgements

CHL and his research are supported by grants from the IKERBASQUE foundation for science, the Starmer-Smith memorial fund, Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (MINECO) of the Spanish Central Government and FEDER funds (PI12/00663, PIE13/00048, DTS14/00109, PI15/00275), Departamento de Desarrollo Económico y Competitividad y Departamento de Sanidad of the Basque government, Asociación Española Contra el Cancer (AECC), and the Diputación Foral de Guipuzcoa (DFG).

References

- [1] K.V. Morris, J.S. Mattick, The rise of regulatory RNA, *Nat Rev Genet* 15(6) (2014) 423-37.
- [2] H.L. Sanger, G. Klotz, D. Riesner, H.J. Gross, A.K. Kleinschmidt, Viroids are single-stranded covalently closed circular RNA molecules existing as highly base-paired rod-like structures, *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 73(11) (1976) 3852-6.
- [3] H.J. Gross, H. Domdey, C. Lossow, P. Jank, M. Raba, H. Alberty, H.L. Sanger, Nucleotide sequence and secondary structure of potato spindle tuber viroid, *Nature* 273(5659) (1978) 203-8.
- [4] A. Kos, R. Dijkema, A.C. Arnberg, P.H. van der Meide, H. Schellekens, The hepatitis delta (delta) virus possesses a circular RNA, *Nature* 323(6088) (1986) 558-60.
- [5] J.M. Nigro, K.R. Cho, E.R. Fearon, S.E. Kern, J.M. Ruppert, J.D. Oliner, K.W. Kinzler, B. Vogelstein, Scrambled exons, *Cell* 64(3) (1991) 607-13.
- [6] C. Cocquerelle, P. Daubersies, M.A. Majerus, J.P. Kerckaert, B. Bailleul, Splicing with inverted order of exons occurs proximal to large introns, *EMBO J* 11(3) (1992) 1095-8.
- [7] B. Capel, A. Swain, S. Nicolis, A. Hacker, M. Walter, P. Koopman, P. Goodfellow, R. Lovell-Badge, Circular transcripts of the testis-determining gene *Sry* in adult mouse testis, *Cell* 73(5) (1993) 1019-30.
- [8] P.G. Zaphiropoulos, Circular RNAs from transcripts of the rat cytochrome P450 2C24 gene: correlation with exon skipping, *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 93(13) (1996) 6536-41.
- [9] P.G. Zaphiropoulos, Exon skipping and circular RNA formation in transcripts of the human cytochrome P-450 2C18 gene in epidermis and of the rat androgen binding protein gene in testis, *Mol Cell Biol* 17(6) (1997) 2985-93.
- [10] A. Surono, T. Van Khanh, Y. Takeshima, H. Wada, M. Yagi, M. Takagi, M. Koizumi, M. Matsuo, Chimeric RNA/ethylene-bridged nucleic acids promote dystrophin expression in myocytes of duchenne muscular dystrophy by inducing skipping of the nonsense mutation-encoding exon, *Hum Gene Ther* 15(8) (2004) 749-57.
- [11] J.M. Houseley, Z. Garcia-Casado, M. Pascual, N. Paricio, K.M. O'Dell, D.G. Monckton, R.D. Artero, Noncanonical RNAs from transcripts of the *Drosophila* muscleblind gene, *J Hered* 97(3) (2006) 253-60.
- [12] X.F. Li, J. Lytton, A circularized sodium-calcium exchanger exon 2 transcript, *J Biol Chem* 274(12) (1999) 8153-60.
- [13] C.E. Burd, W.R. Jeck, Y. Liu, H.K. Sanoff, Z. Wang, N.E. Sharpless, Expression of linear and novel circular forms of an INK4/ARF-associated non-coding RNA correlates with atherosclerosis risk, *PLoS Genet* 6(12) (2010) e1001233.
- [14] T.B. Hansen, E.D. Wiklund, J.B. Bramsen, S.B. Villadsen, A.L. Statham, S.J. Clark, J. Kjems, miRNA-dependent gene silencing involving Ago2-mediated cleavage of a circular antisense RNA, *EMBO J* 30(21) (2011) 4414-22.
- [15] M. Danan, S. Schwartz, S. Edelheit, R. Sorek, Transcriptome-wide discovery of circular RNAs in *Archaea*, *Nucleic Acids Res* 40(7) (2012) 3131-42.
- [16] C. Cocquerelle, B. Mascrez, D. Hetuin, B. Bailleul, Mis-splicing yields circular RNA molecules, *FASEB J* 7(1) (1993) 155-60.
- [17] W.R. Jeck, J.A. Sorrentino, K. Wang, M.K. Slevin, C.E. Burd, J. Liu, W.F. Marzluff, N.E. Sharpless, Circular RNAs are abundant, conserved, and associated with ALU repeats, *RNA* 19(2) (2013) 141-57.
- [18] A. Rybak-Wolf, C. Stottmeister, P. Glazar, M. Jens, N. Pino, S. Giusti, M. Hanan, M. Behm, O. Bartok, R. Ashwal-Fluss, M. Herzog, L. Schreyer, P. Papavasileiou, A. Ivanov, M. Ohman, D. Refojo, S. Kadener, N. Rajewsky, Circular RNAs in the Mammalian Brain Are Highly Abundant, Conserved, and Dynamically Expressed, *Mol Cell* 58(5) (2015) 870-85.
- [19] J. Salzman, C. Gawad, P.L. Wang, N. Lacayo, P.O. Brown, Circular RNAs are the predominant transcript isoform from hundreds of human genes in diverse cell types, *PloS one* 7(2) (2012) e30733.
- [20] H. Suzuki, Y. Zuo, J. Wang, M.Q. Zhang, A. Malhotra, A. Mayeda, Characterization of RNase R-digested cellular RNA source that consists of lariat and circular RNAs from pre-mRNA splicing, *Nucleic acids research* 34(8) (2006) e63.

- [21] H.A. Vincent, M.P. Deutscher, Substrate recognition and catalysis by the exoribonuclease RNase R, *The Journal of biological chemistry* 281(40) (2006) 29769-75.
- [22] W.R. Jeck, N.E. Sharpless, Detecting and characterizing circular RNAs, *Nature biotechnology* 32(5) (2014) 453-61.
- [23] Z. Li, C. Huang, C. Bao, L. Chen, M. Lin, X. Wang, G. Zhong, B. Yu, W. Hu, L. Dai, P. Zhu, Z. Chang, Q. Wu, Y. Zhao, Y. Jia, P. Xu, H. Liu, G. Shan, Exon-intron circular RNAs regulate transcription in the nucleus, *Nat Struct Mol Biol* 22(3) (2015) 256-64.
- [24] S. Memczak, M. Jens, A. Elefsinioti, F. Torti, J. Krueger, A. Rybak, L. Maier, S.D. Mackowiak, L.H. Gregersen, M. Munschauer, A. Loewer, U. Ziebold, M. Landthaler, C. Kocks, F. le Noble, N. Rajewsky, Circular RNAs are a large class of animal RNAs with regulatory potency, *Nature* 495(7441) (2013) 333-8.
- [25] J. Salzman, R.E. Chen, M.N. Olsen, P.L. Wang, P.O. Brown, Cell-type specific features of circular RNA expression, *PLoS Genet* 9(9) (2013) e1003777.
- [26] G.J.S. Talhouarne, J.G. Gall, Lariat intronic RNAs in the cytoplasm of vertebrate cells, *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 115(34) (2018) E7970-E7977.
- [27] X. Meng, X. Li, P. Zhang, J. Wang, Y. Zhou, M. Chen, Circular RNA: an emerging key player in RNA world, *Brief Bioinform* 18(4) (2017) 547-557.
- [28] Z. Lu, G.S. Filonov, J.J. Noto, C.A. Schmidt, T.L. Hatkevich, Y. Wen, S.R. Jaffrey, A.G. Matera, Metazoan tRNA introns generate stable circular RNAs in vivo, *RNA* 21(9) (2015) 1554-65.
- [29] Y. Zhang, X.O. Zhang, T. Chen, J.F. Xiang, Q.F. Yin, Y.H. Xing, S. Zhu, L. Yang, L.L. Chen, Circular intronic long noncoding RNAs, *Mol Cell* 51(6) (2013) 792-806.
- [30] X.O. Zhang, H.B. Wang, Y. Zhang, X. Lu, L.L. Chen, L. Yang, Complementary sequence-mediated exon circularization, *Cell* 159(1) (2014) 134-147.
- [31] A. Ivanov, S. Memczak, E. Wyler, F. Torti, H.T. Porath, M.R. Orejuela, M. Piechotta, E.Y. Levanon, M. Landthaler, C. Dieterich, N. Rajewsky, Analysis of intron sequences reveals hallmarks of circular RNA biogenesis in animals, *Cell reports* 10(2) (2015) 170-7.
- [32] D. Liang, J.E. Wilusz, Short intronic repeat sequences facilitate circular RNA production, *Genes & development* 28(20) (2014) 2233-47.
- [33] S.P. Barrett, P.L. Wang, J. Salzman, Circular RNA biogenesis can proceed through an exon-containing lariat precursor, *eLife* 4 (2015) e07540.
- [34] E. Lasda, R. Parker, Circular RNAs: diversity of form and function, *RNA (New York, N.Y.)* 20(12) (2014) 1829-42.
- [35] Q. Vicens, E. Westhof, Biogenesis of Circular RNAs, *Cell* 159(1) (2014) 13-14.
- [36] R. Ashwal-Fluss, M. Meyer, N.R. Pamudurti, A. Ivanov, O. Bartok, M. Hanan, N. Evantal, S. Memczak, N. Rajewsky, S. Kadener, circRNA biogenesis competes with pre-mRNA splicing, *Mol Cell* 56(1) (2014) 55-66.
- [37] T. Aktas, I. Avsar Ilik, D. Maticzka, V. Bhardwaj, C. Pessoa Rodrigues, G. Mittler, T. Manke, R. Backofen, A. Akhtar, DHX9 suppresses RNA processing defects originating from the Alu invasion of the human genome, *Nature* 544(7648) (2017) 115-119.
- [38] C.H. Lawrie, *MicroRNAs in Medicine*, Wiley, New York, 2014.
- [39] Y. Tay, J. Rinn, P.P. Pandolfi, The multilayered complexity of ceRNA crosstalk and competition, *Nature* 505(7483) (2014) 344-52.
- [40] T.B. Hansen, T.I. Jensen, B.H. Clausen, J.B. Bramsen, B. Finsen, C.K. Damgaard, J. Kjems, Natural RNA circles function as efficient microRNA sponges, *Nature* 495(7441) (2013) 384-8.
- [41] J.U. Guo, V. Agarwal, H. Guo, D.P. Bartel, Expanded identification and characterization of mammalian circular RNAs, *Genome Biol* 15(7) (2014) 409.
- [42] X. You, I. Vlatkovic, A. Babic, T. Will, I. Epstein, G. Tushev, G. Akbalik, M. Wang, C. Glock, C. Quedenau, X. Wang, J. Hou, H. Liu, W. Sun, S. Sambandan, T. Chen, E.M. Schuman, W. Chen, Neural circular RNAs are derived from synaptic genes and regulated by development and plasticity, *Nat Neurosci* 18(4) (2015) 603-610.
- [43] C.W. Chao, D.C. Chan, A. Kuo, P. Leder, The mouse formin (*Fmn*) gene: abundant circular RNA transcripts and gene-targeted deletion analysis, *Molecular medicine (Cambridge, Mass.)* 4(9) (1998) 614-28.

- [44] W.W. Du, W. Yang, Y. Chen, Z.K. Wu, F.S. Foster, Z. Yang, X. Li, B.B. Yang, Foxo3 circular RNA promotes cardiac senescence by modulating multiple factors associated with stress and senescence responses, *Eur Heart J* 38(18) (2017) 1402-1412.
- [45] L.M. Holdt, A. Stahlinger, K. Sass, G. Pichler, N.A. Kulak, W. Wilfert, A. Kohlmaier, A. Herbst, B.H. Northoff, A. Nicolaou, G. Gabel, F. Beutner, M. Scholz, J. Thiery, K. Musunuru, K. Krohn, M. Mann, D. Teupser, Circular non-coding RNA ANRIL modulates ribosomal RNA maturation and atherosclerosis in humans, *Nat Commun* 7 (2016) 12429.
- [46] C.Y. Chen, P. Sarnow, Initiation of protein synthesis by the eukaryotic translational apparatus on circular RNAs, *Science* 268(5209) (1995) 415-7.
- [47] I. Legnini, G. Di Timoteo, F. Rossi, M. Morlando, F. Briganti, O. Sthandier, A. Fatica, T. Santini, A. Andronache, M. Wade, P. Laneve, N. Rajewsky, I. Bozzoni, Circ-ZNF609 Is a Circular RNA that Can Be Translated and Functions in Myogenesis, *Mol Cell* 66(1) (2017) 22-37 e9.
- [48] N.R. Pamudurti, O. Bartok, M. Jens, R. Ashwal-Fluss, C. Stottmeister, L. Ruhe, M. Hanan, E. Wyler, D. Perez-Hernandez, E. Ramberger, S. Shenzen, M. Samson, G. Dittmar, M. Landthaler, M. Chekulaeva, N. Rajewsky, S. Kadener, Translation of CircRNAs, *Mol Cell* 66(1) (2017) 9-21 e7.
- [49] Y. Zhang, W. Xue, X. Li, J. Zhang, S. Chen, J.L. Zhang, L. Yang, L.L. Chen, The Biogenesis of Nascent Circular RNAs, *Cell Rep* 15(3) (2016) 611-624.
- [50] J.O. Westholm, P. Miura, S. Olson, S. Shenker, B. Joseph, P. Sanfilippo, S.E. Celniker, B.R. Graveley, E.C. Lai, Genome-wide analysis of drosophila circular RNAs reveals their structural and sequence properties and age-dependent neural accumulation, *Cell Rep* 9(5) (2014) 1966-1980.
- [51] E. Buratti, F.E. Baralle, TDP-43: new aspects of autoregulation mechanisms in RNA binding proteins and their connection with human disease, *FEBS J* 278(19) (2011) 3530-8.
- [52] R.J. Osborne, C.A. Thornton, RNA-dominant diseases, *Hum Mol Genet* 15 Spec No 2 (2006) R162-9.
- [53] S. Yue, H.G. Serra, H.Y. Zoghbi, H.T. Orr, The spinocerebellar ataxia type 1 protein, ataxin-1, has RNA-binding activity that is inversely affected by the length of its polyglutamine tract, *Hum Mol Genet* 10(1) (2001) 25-30.
- [54] W.J. Lukiw, Circular RNA (circRNA) in Alzheimer's disease (AD), *Front Genet* 4 (2013) 307.
- [55] M. Piwecka, P. Glazar, L.R. Hernandez-Miranda, S. Memczak, S.A. Wolf, A. Rybak-Wolf, A. Filipchyk, F. Klironomos, C.A. Cerda Jara, P. Fenske, T. Trimbuch, V. Zywitzka, M. Plass, L. Schreyer, S. Ayoub, C. Kocks, R. Kuhn, C. Rosenmund, C. Birchmeier, N. Rajewsky, Loss of a mammalian circular RNA locus causes miRNA deregulation and affects brain function, *Science* 357(6357) (2017).
- [56] Y.G. Chen, M.V. Kim, X. Chen, P.J. Batista, S. Aoyama, J.E. Wilusz, A. Iwasaki, H.Y. Chang, Sensing Self and Foreign Circular RNAs by Intron Identity, *Mol Cell* 67(2) (2017) 228-238 e5.
- [57] X. Li, C.X. Liu, W. Xue, Y. Zhang, S. Jiang, Q.F. Yin, J. Wei, R.W. Yao, L. Yang, L.L. Chen, Coordinated circRNA Biogenesis and Function with NF90/NF110 in Viral Infection, *Mol Cell* 67(2) (2017) 214-227 e7.
- [58] P. Xia, S. Wang, B. Ye, Y. Du, C. Li, Z. Xiong, Y. Qu, Z. Fan, A Circular RNA Protects Dormant Hematopoietic Stem Cells from DNA Sensor cGAS-Mediated Exhaustion, *Immunity* 48(4) (2018) 688-701 e7.
- [59] S. Memczak, P. Papavasileiou, O. Peters, N. Rajewsky, Identification and Characterization of Circular RNAs As a New Class of Putative Biomarkers in Human Blood, *PLoS One* 10(10) (2015) e0141214.
- [60] W.L. Tan, B.T. Lim, C.G. Anene-Nzeli, M. Ackers-Johnson, A. Dashi, K. See, Z. Tiang, D.P. Lee, W.W. Chua, T.D. Luu, P.Y. Li, A.M. Richards, R.S. Foo, A landscape of circular RNA expression in the human heart, *Cardiovasc Res* 113(3) (2017) 298-309.
- [61] K. Wang, B. Long, F. Liu, J.X. Wang, C.Y. Liu, B. Zhao, L.Y. Zhou, T. Sun, M. Wang, T. Yu, Y. Gong, J. Liu, Y.H. Dong, N. Li, P.F. Li, A circular RNA protects the heart from pathological hypertrophy and heart failure by targeting miR-223, *Eur Heart J* 37(33) (2016) 2602-11.
- [62] C.M. Tang, M. Zhang, L. Huang, Z.Q. Hu, J.N. Zhu, Z. Xiao, Z. Zhang, Q.X. Lin, X.L. Zheng, M. Yang, S.L. Wu, J.D. Cheng, Z.X. Shan, CircRNA_000203 enhances the expression of fibrosis-associated genes by derepressing targets of miR-26b-5p, *Colla2* and *CTGF*, in cardiac fibroblasts, *Sci Rep* 7 (2017) 40342.

- [63] B. Zhou, J.W. Yu, A novel identified circular RNA, circRNA_010567, promotes myocardial fibrosis via suppressing miR-141 by targeting TGF-beta1, *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 487(4) (2017) 769-775.
- [64] M. Vausort, A. Salgado-Somoza, L. Zhang, P. Leszek, M. Scholz, A. Teren, R. Burkhardt, J. Thiery, D.R. Wagner, Y. Devaux, Myocardial Infarction-Associated Circular RNA Predicting Left Ventricular Dysfunction, *J Am Coll Cardiol* 68(11) (2016) 1247-1248.
- [65] J. Zhang, H. Liu, L. Hou, G. Wang, R. Zhang, Y. Huang, X. Chen, J. Zhu, Circular RNA_LARP4 inhibits cell proliferation and invasion of gastric cancer by sponging miR-424-5p and regulating LATS1 expression, *Molecular cancer* 16(1) (2017) 151.
- [66] D. Han, J. Li, H. Wang, X. Su, J. Hou, Y. Gu, C. Qian, Y. Lin, X. Liu, M. Huang, N. Li, W. Zhou, Y. Yu, X. Cao, Circular RNA circMTO1 acts as the sponge of microRNA-9 to suppress hepatocellular carcinoma progression, *Hepatology* 66(4) (2017) 1151-1164.
- [67] X.Y. Huang, Z.L. Huang, Y.H. Xu, Q. Zheng, Z. Chen, W. Song, J. Zhou, Z.Y. Tang, X.Y. Huang, Comprehensive circular RNA profiling reveals the regulatory role of the circRNA-100338/miR-141-3p pathway in hepatitis B-related hepatocellular carcinoma, *Sci Rep* 7(1) (2017) 5428.
- [68] Z. Yao, J. Luo, K. Hu, J. Lin, H. Huang, Q. Wang, P. Zhang, Z. Xiong, C. He, Z. Huang, B. Liu, Y. Yang, ZKSCAN1 gene and its related circular RNA (circZKSCAN1) both inhibit hepatocellular carcinoma cell growth, migration, and invasion but through different signaling pathways, *Mol Oncol* 11(4) (2017) 422-437.
- [69] X. Yang, Q. Xiong, Y. Wu, S. Li, F. Ge, Quantitative Proteomics Reveals the Regulatory Networks of Circular RNA CDR1as in Hepatocellular Carcinoma Cells, *J Proteome Res* 16(10) (2017) 3891-3902.
- [70] U. Schulze-Gahmen, S.H. Kim, Structural basis for CDK6 activation by a virus-encoded cyclin, *Nat Struct Biol* 9(3) (2002) 177-81.
- [71] H. Xie, X. Ren, S. Xin, X. Lan, G. Lu, Y. Lin, S. Yang, Z. Zeng, W. Liao, Y.Q. Ding, L. Liang, Emerging roles of circRNA_001569 targeting miR-145 in the proliferation and invasion of colorectal cancer, *Oncotarget* 7(18) (2016) 26680-91.
- [72] X.L. Zhang, L.L. Xu, F. Wang, Hsa_circ_0020397 regulates colorectal cancer cell viability, apoptosis and invasion by promoting the expression of the miR-138 targets TERT and PD-L1, *Cell Biol Int* 41(9) (2017) 1056-1064.
- [73] L. Wan, L. Zhang, K. Fan, Z.X. Cheng, Q.C. Sun, J.J. Wang, Circular RNA-ITCH Suppresses Lung Cancer Proliferation via Inhibiting the Wnt/beta-Catenin Pathway, *Biomed Res Int* 2016 (2016) 1579490.
- [74] H.F. Liang, X.Z. Zhang, B.G. Liu, G.T. Jia, W.L. Li, Circular RNA circ-ABCB10 promotes breast cancer proliferation and progression through sponging miR-1271, *Am J Cancer Res* 7(7) (2017) 1566-1576.
- [75] Y.Y. Tang, P. Zhao, T.N. Zou, J.J. Duan, R. Zhi, S.Y. Yang, D.C. Yang, X.L. Wang, Circular RNA hsa_circ_0001982 Promotes Breast Cancer Cell Carcinogenesis Through Decreasing miR-143, *DNA Cell Biol* 36(11) (2017) 901-908.
- [76] G. Liang, Z. Liu, L. Tan, A.N. Su, W.G. Jiang, C. Gong, HIF1alpha-associated circDENND4C Promotes Proliferation of Breast Cancer Cells in Hypoxic Environment, *Anticancer Res* 37(8) (2017) 4337-4343.
- [77] J.H. Bahn, Q. Zhang, F. Li, T.M. Chan, X. Lin, Y. Kim, D.T. Wong, X. Xiao, The landscape of microRNA, Piwi-interacting RNA, and circular RNA in human saliva, *Clinical chemistry* 61(1) (2015) 221-30.
- [78] W. Weng, Q. Wei, S. Toden, K. Yoshida, T. Nagasaka, T. Fujiwara, S. Cai, H. Qin, Y. Ma, A. Goel, Circular RNA ciRS-7-A Promising Prognostic Biomarker and a Potential Therapeutic Target in Colorectal Cancer, *Clinical cancer research : an official journal of the American Association for Cancer Research* 23(14) (2017) 3918-3928.
- [79] H. Pan, T. Li, Y. Jiang, C. Pan, Y. Ding, Z. Huang, H. Yu, D. Kong, Overexpression of Circular RNA ciRS-7 Abrogates the Tumor Suppressive Effect of miR-7 on Gastric Cancer via PTEN/PI3K/AKT Signaling Pathway, *J Cell Biochem* 119(1) (2018) 440-446.

- [80] M. Sang, L. Meng, Y. Sang, S. Liu, P. Ding, Y. Ju, F. Liu, L. Gu, Y. Lian, J. Li, Y. Wu, X. Zhang, B. Shan, Circular RNA ciRS-7 accelerates ESCC progression through acting as a miR-876-5p sponge to enhance MAGE-A family expression, *Cancer Lett* 426 (2018) 37-46.
- [81] L. Xu, M. Zhang, X. Zheng, P. Yi, C. Lan, M. Xu, The circular RNA ciRS-7 (Cdr1as) acts as a risk factor of hepatic microvascular invasion in hepatocellular carcinoma, *J Cancer Res Clin Oncol* 143(1) (2017) 17-27.
- [82] G. Huang, H. Zhu, Y. Shi, W. Wu, H. Cai, X. Chen, cir-ITCH plays an inhibitory role in colorectal cancer by regulating the Wnt/beta-catenin pathway, *PloS one* 10(6) (2015) e0131225.
- [83] L. Wan, L. Zhang, K. Fan, Z.X. Cheng, Q.C. Sun, J.J. Wang, Circular RNA-ITCH Suppresses Lung Cancer Proliferation via Inhibiting the Wnt/beta-Catenin Pathway, 2016 (2016) 1579490.
- [84] F. Li, L. Zhang, W. Li, J. Deng, J. Zheng, M. An, J. Lu, Y. Zhou, Circular RNA ITCH has inhibitory effect on ESCC by suppressing the Wnt/beta-catenin pathway, *Oncotarget* 6(8) (2015) 6001-13.
- [85] W. Guo, J. Zhang, D. Zhang, S. Cao, G. Li, S. Zhang, Z. Wang, P. Wen, H. Yang, X. Shi, J. Pan, H. Ye, Polymorphisms and expression pattern of circular RNA circ-ITCH contributes to the carcinogenesis of hepatocellular carcinoma, *Oncotarget* 8(29) (2017) 48169-48177.
- [86] Y. Zhang, H. Zhao, L. Zhang, Identification of the tumorsuppressive function of circular RNA FOXO3 in non-small cell lung cancer through sponging miR155, *Molecular medicine reports* 17(6) (2018) 7692-7700.
- [87] W.W. Du, L. Fang, W. Yang, N. Wu, F.M. Awan, Z. Yang, B.B. Yang, Induction of tumor apoptosis through a circular RNA enhancing Foxo3 activity, *Cell Death Differ* 24(2) (2017) 357-370.
- [88] J. Chen, Y. Li, Q. Zheng, C. Bao, J. He, B. Chen, D. Lyu, B. Zheng, Y. Xu, Z. Long, Y. Zhou, H. Zhu, Y. Wang, X. He, Y. Shi, S. Huang, Circular RNA profile identifies circPVT1 as a proliferative factor and prognostic marker in gastric cancer, *Cancer letters* 388 (2017) 208-219.
- [89] P. Li, S. Chen, H. Chen, X. Mo, T. Li, Y. Shao, B. Xiao, J. Guo, Using circular RNA as a novel type of biomarker in the screening of gastric cancer, *Clinica chimica acta; international journal of clinical chemistry* 444 (2015) 132-6.
- [90] S. Chen, T. Li, Q. Zhao, B. Xiao, J. Guo, Using circular RNA hsa_circ_0000190 as a new biomarker in the diagnosis of gastric cancer, *Disease markers* 466 (2017) 167-171.
- [91] X. Zhang, Y. Zhang, H. Liu, W. Li, J. Yu, J. Li, Z. Shen, G. Ye, X. Qi, G. Li, CircRNA_100269 is downregulated in gastric cancer and suppresses tumor cell growth by targeting miR-630, *Journal of clinical laboratory analysis* 9(6) (2017) 1585-1594.
- [92] Y. Zhang, J. Li, J. Yu, H. Liu, Z. Shen, G. Ye, T. Mou, X. Qi, G. Li, Circular RNAs signature predicts the early recurrence of stage III gastric cancer after radical surgery, *Oncotarget* 8(14) (2017) 22936-22943.
- [93] X. Shang, G. Li, H. Liu, T. Li, J. Liu, Q. Zhao, C. Wang, Comprehensive Circular RNA Profiling Reveals That hsa_circ_0005075, a New Circular RNA Biomarker, Is Involved in Hepatocellular Carcinoma Development, *Medicine* 95(22) (2016) e3811.
- [94] M. Qin, G. Liu, X. Huo, X. Tao, X. Sun, Z. Ge, J. Yang, J. Fan, L. Liu, W. Qin, Hsa_circ_0001649: A circular RNA and potential novel biomarker for hepatocellular carcinoma, *Cancer biomarkers : section A of Disease markers* 16(1) (2016) 161-9.
- [95] M. Berretta, C. Cavaliere, L. Alessandrini, B. Stanzione, G. Facchini, L. Balestreri, T. Perin, V. Canzonieri, Serum and tissue markers in hepatocellular carcinoma and cholangiocarcinoma: clinical and prognostic implications, *Oncotarget* 8(8) (2017) 14192-14220.
- [96] X. Zhu, X. Wang, S. Wei, Y. Chen, Y. Chen, X. Fan, S. Han, G. Wu, hsa_circ_0013958: a circular RNA and potential novel biomarker for lung adenocarcinoma, *The FEBS journal* 284(14) (2017) 2170-2182.
- [97] J.T. Yao, S.H. Zhao, Q.P. Liu, M.Q. Lv, D.X. Zhou, Z.J. Liao, K.J. Nan, Over-expression of CircRNA_100876 in non-small cell lung cancer and its prognostic value, *Pathology, research and practice* 213(5) (2017) 453-456.
- [98] J. Zhao, L. Li, Q. Wang, H. Han, Q. Zhan, M. Xu, CircRNA Expression Profile in Early-Stage Lung Adenocarcinoma Patients, *Cell Physiol Biochem* 44(6) (2017) 2138-2146.
- [99] L. Szabo, J. Salzman, Detecting circular RNAs: bioinformatic and experimental challenges, *Nat Rev Genet* 17(11) (2016) 679-692.

- [100] P.L. Wang, Y. Bao, M.C. Yee, S.P. Barrett, G.J. Hogan, M.N. Olsen, J.R. Dinneny, P.O. Brown, J. Salzman, Circular RNA is expressed across the eukaryotic tree of life, *PLoS One* 9(6) (2014) e90859.
- [101] C.K. Roy, S. Olson, B.R. Graveley, P.D. Zamore, M.J. Moore, Assessing long-distance RNA sequence connectivity via RNA-templated DNA-DNA ligation, *Elife* 4 (2015).
- [102] J. Cocquet, A. Chong, G. Zhang, R.A. Veitia, Reverse transcriptase template switching and false alternative transcripts, *Genomics* 88(1) (2006) 127-31.
- [103] N. Abe, K. Matsumoto, M. Nishihara, Y. Nakano, A. Shibata, H. Maruyama, S. Shuto, A. Matsuda, M. Yoshida, Y. Ito, H. Abe, Rolling Circle Translation of Circular RNA in Living Human Cells, *Sci Rep* 5 (2015) 16435.
- [104] M.A. Quail, I. Kozarewa, F. Smith, A. Scally, P.J. Stephens, R. Durbin, H. Swerdlow, D.J. Turner, A large genome center's improvements to the Illumina sequencing system, *Nat Methods* 5(12) (2008) 1005-10.
- [105] X. Zeng, W. Lin, M. Guo, Q. Zou, A comprehensive overview and evaluation of circular RNA detection tools, *PLoS Comput Biol* 13(6) (2017) e1005420.
- [106] T.B. Hansen, M.T. Veno, C.K. Damgaard, J. Kjems, Comparison of circular RNA prediction tools, *Nucleic Acids Res* 44(6) (2016) e58.
- [107] M. Cortes-Lopez, P. Miura, Emerging Functions of Circular RNAs, *Yale J Biol Med* 89(4) (2016) 527-537.
- [108] S. Chen, L. Zhang, Y. Su, X. Zhang, Screening potential biomarkers for colorectal cancer based on circular RNA chips, *Oncology reports* 39(6) (2018) 2499-2512.
- [109] M. Zhu, Y. Xu, Y. Chen, F. Yan, Circular BANP, an upregulated circular RNA that modulates cell proliferation in colorectal cancer, *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy = Biomedecine & pharmacotherapie* 88 (2017) 138-144.
- [110] F. Wang, J. Wang, X. Cao, L. Xu, L. Chen, Hsa_circ_0014717 is downregulated in colorectal cancer and inhibits tumor growth by promoting p16 expression, *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy = Biomedecine & pharmacotherapie* 98 (2018) 775-782.
- [111] K. Zeng, X. Chen, M. Xu, X. Liu, X. Hu, T. Xu, H. Sun, Y. Pan, B. He, S. Wang, CircHIPK3 promotes colorectal cancer growth and metastasis by sponging miR-7, *Cell death & disease* 9(4) (2018) 417.
- [112] W. Ji, C. Qiu, M. Wang, N. Mao, S. Wu, Y. Dai, Hsa_circ_0001649: A circular RNA and potential novel biomarker for colorectal cancer, *Biochemical and biophysical research communications* 497(1) (2018) 122-126.
- [113] J. Wang, X. Li, Circular RNA hsa_circ_0000567 can be used as a promising diagnostic biomarker for human colorectal cancer, *32(5)* (2018) e22379.
- [114] L. Lu, L. He, H. Hu, Z. Xu, X.W. Xu, B.A. Zheng, Z.M. Hu, Z.Y. Qian, C.J. Huang, X.Q. Liu, W.D. Wu, Circular RNA hsa_circ_000984 promotes colon cancer growth and metastasis by sponging miR-106b, *Journal of clinical laboratory analysis* 8(53) (2017) 91674-91683.
- [115] F. Zhuo, H. Lin, Z. Chen, Z. Huang, J. Hu, The expression profile and clinical significance of circRNA0003906 in colorectal cancer, *OncoTargets and therapy* 10 (2017) 5187-5193.
- [116] P. Zhang, Z. Zuo, W. Shang, A. Wu, R. Bi, J. Wu, S. Li, X. Sun, L. Jiang, Identification of differentially expressed circular RNAs in human colorectal cancer, *Tumour biology : the journal of the International Society for Oncodevelopmental Biology and Medicine* 39(3) (2017) 1010428317694546.
- [117] K.Y. Hsiao, Y.C. Lin, S.K. Gupta, N. Chang, L. Yen, H.S. Sun, S.J. Tsai, Noncoding Effects of Circular RNA CCDC66 Promote Colon Cancer Growth and Metastasis, *Cancer research* 77(9) (2017) 2339-2350.
- [118] J.N. Guo, J. Li, C.L. Zhu, W.T. Feng, J.X. Shao, L. Wan, M.D. Huang, J.D. He, Comprehensive profile of differentially expressed circular RNAs reveals that hsa_circ_0000069 is upregulated and promotes cell proliferation, migration, and invasion in colorectal cancer, *OncoTargets and therapy* 9 (2016) 7451-7458.
- [119] X. Wang, Y. Zhang, L. Huang, J. Zhang, F. Pan, B. Li, Y. Yan, B. Jia, H. Liu, S. Li, W. Zheng, Decreased expression of hsa_circ_001988 in colorectal cancer and its clinical significances, *International journal of clinical and experimental pathology* 8(12) (2015) 16020-5.

- [120] D. Hang, J. Zhou, N. Qin, W. Zhou, H. Ma, G. Jin, Z. Hu, J. Dai, H. Shen, A novel plasma circular RNA circFARSA is a potential biomarker for non-small cell lung cancer, *Cancer medicine* 7(6) (2018) 2783-2791.
- [121] L. Wang, S. Liu, Y. Mao, J. Xu, S. Yang, H. Shen, W. Xu, W. Fan, J. Wang, CircRNF13 regulates the invasion and metastasis in lung adenocarcinoma by targeting miR-93-5p, *Gene* (2018).
- [122] S. Tan, Q. Gou, W. Pu, Circular RNA F-circEA produced from EML4-ALK fusion gene as a novel liquid biopsy biomarker for non-small cell lung cancer, 28(6) (2018) 693-695.
- [123] X. Ma, X. Yang, W. Bao, S. Li, S. Liang, Y. Sun, Y. Zhao, J. Wang, C. Zhao, Circular RNA circMAN2B2 facilitates lung cancer cell proliferation and invasion via miR-1275/FOXK1 axis, *Biochemical and biophysical research communications* 498(4) (2018) 1009-1015.
- [124] X. Wang, X. Zhu, H. Zhang, S. Wei, Y. Chen, Y. Chen, F. Wang, X. Fan, S. Han, G. Wu, Increased circular RNA hsa_circ_0012673 acts as a sponge of miR-22 to promote lung adenocarcinoma proliferation, *Biochemical and biophysical research communications* 496(4) (2018) 1069-1075.
- [125] Y.H. Luo, X.Z. Zhu, K.W. Huang, Q. Zhang, Y.X. Fan, P.W. Yan, J. Wen, Emerging roles of circular RNA hsa_circ_0000064 in the proliferation and metastasis of lung cancer, *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy = Biomedecine & pharmacotherapie* 96 (2017) 892-898.
- [126] W. Liu, W. Ma, Y. Yuan, Y. Zhang, S. Sun, Circular RNA hsa_circRNA_103809 promotes lung cancer progression via facilitating ZNF121-dependent MYC expression by sequestering miR-4302, *BioMed research international* 500(4) (2018) 846-851.
- [127] J. Li, J. Wang, Z. Chen, Y. Chen, M. Jin, Hsa_circ_0079530 promotes cell proliferation and invasion in non-small cell lung cancer, *Gene* 665 (2018) 1-5.
- [128] M. Qiu, W. Xia, R. Chen, S. Wang, Y. Xu, Z. Ma, W. Xu, E. Zhang, J. Wang, T. Fang, J. Hu, G. Dong, R. Yin, J. Wang, L. Xu, The Circular RNA circPRKCI Promotes Tumor Growth in Lung Adenocarcinoma, *Cancer research* 78(11) (2018) 2839-2851.
- [129] S. Zhang, X. Zeng, T. Ding, L. Guo, Y. Li, S. Ou, H. Yuan, Microarray profile of circular RNAs identifies hsa_circ_0014130 as a new circular RNA biomarker in non-small cell lung cancer, *Scientific reports* 8(1) (2018) 2878.
- [130] T. Liu, S. Liu, Y. Xu, R. Shu, F. Wang, C. Chen, Y. Zeng, H. Luo, Circular RNA-ZFR Inhibited Cell Proliferation and Promoted Apoptosis in Gastric Cancer by Sponging miR-130a/miR-107 and Modulating PTEN, *Cancer research and treatment : official journal of Korean Cancer Association* 50(4) (2018) 1396-1417.
- [131] A.F. Vidal, A.M. Ribeiro-Dos-Santos, T. Vinasco-Sandoval, L. Magalhaes, P. Pinto, A.K.M. Anaissi, S. Demachki, P.P. de Assumpcao, S.E.B. Dos Santos, A. Ribeiro-Dos-Santos, The comprehensive expression analysis of circular RNAs in gastric cancer and its association with field cancerization, 7(1) (2017) 14551.
- [132] T. Li, Y. Shao, L. Fu, Y. Xie, L. Zhu, W. Sun, R. Yu, B. Xiao, J. Guo, Plasma circular RNA profiling of patients with gastric cancer and their droplet digital RT-PCR detection, *Scientific reports* 96(1) (2018) 85-96.
- [133] Z. Lai, Y. Yang, Y. Yan, T. Li, Y. Li, Z. Wang, Z. Shen, Y. Ye, K. Jiang, S. Wang, Analysis of co-expression networks for circular RNAs and mRNAs reveals that circular RNAs hsa_circ_0047905, hsa_circ_0138960 and has-circRNA7690-15 are candidate oncogenes in gastric cancer, *Journal of molecular medicine (Berlin, Germany)* 16(23) (2017) 2301-2311.
- [134] H. Sun, W. Tang, D. Rong, H. Jin, K. Fu, W. Zhang, Z. Liu, H. Cao, X. Cao, Hsa_circ_0000520, a potential new circular RNA biomarker, is involved in gastric carcinoma, *Cancer biomarkers : section A of Disease markers* 21(2) (2018) 299-306.
- [135] M. Huang, Y.R. He, L.C. Liang, Q. Huang, Z.Q. Zhu, Circular RNA hsa_circ_0000745 may serve as a diagnostic marker for gastric cancer, *World journal of gastroenterology* 23(34) (2017) 6330-6338.
- [136] Q. Zhao, S. Chen, T. Li, B. Xiao, Clinical values of circular RNA 0000181 in the screening of gastric cancer, 32(4) (2018) e22333.
- [137] J. Li, L. Zhen, Y. Zhang, L. Zhao, H. Liu, D. Cai, H. Chen, J. Yu, X. Qi, G. Li, Circ-104916 is downregulated in gastric cancer and suppresses migration and invasion of gastric cancer cells, *OncoTargets and therapy* 10 (2017) 3521-3529.

- [138] R. Lu, Y. Shao, G. Ye, B. Xiao, J. Guo, Low expression of hsa_circ_0006633 in human gastric cancer and its clinical significances, *Tumour biology : the journal of the International Society for Oncodevelopmental Biology and Medicine* 39(6) (2017) 1010428317704175.
- [139] Y. Fang, M. Ma, J. Wang, X. Liu, Y. Wang, Circular RNAs play an important role in late-stage gastric cancer: Circular RNA expression profiles and bioinformatics analyses, *Tumour biology : the journal of the International Society for Oncodevelopmental Biology and Medicine* 39(6) (2017) 1010428317705850.
- [140] M. Tian, R. Chen, T. Li, B. Xiao, Reduced expression of circRNA hsa_circ_0003159 in gastric cancer and its clinical significance, 32(3) (2018).
- [141] T. Li, Y. Jiang, C. Pan, Y. Ding, Z. Huang, H. Yu, D. Kong, Y. Shao, J. Li, R. Lu, T. Li, Y. Yang, B. Xiao, J. Guo, Global circular RNA expression profile of human gastric cancer and its clinical significance, *Journal of cellular biochemistry* 6(6) (2017) 1173-1180.
- [142] Y. Shao, L. Chen, R. Lu, X. Zhang, B. Xiao, G. Ye, J. Guo, Decreased expression of hsa_circ_0001895 in human gastric cancer and its clinical significances, *Cancer medicine* 39(4) (2017) 1010428317699125.
- [143] W.H. Li, Y.C. Song, H. Zhang, Decreased Expression of Hsa_circ_00001649 in Gastric Cancer and Its Clinical Significance, 2017 (2017) 4587698.
- [144] P. Li, H. Chen, S. Chen, X. Mo, T. Li, B. Xiao, R. Yu, J. Guo, Circular RNA 0000096 affects cell growth and migration in gastric cancer, *British journal of cancer* 116(5) (2017) 626-633.
- [145] H. Wang, Y. Xiao, L. Wu, D. Ma, Comprehensive circular RNA profiling reveals the regulatory role of the circRNA-000911/miR-449a pathway in breast carcinogenesis, *International journal of oncology* 52(3) (2018) 743-754.
- [146] L. Lu, J. Sun, P. Shi, W. Kong, K. Xu, B. He, S. Zhang, J. Wang, Identification of circular RNAs as a promising new class of diagnostic biomarkers for human breast cancer, *Oncotarget* 8(27) (2017) 44096-44107.
- [147] N. Wang, Y. Gu, L. Li, F. Wang, P. Lv, Y. Xiong, X. Qiu, Circular RNA circMYO9B facilitates breast cancer cell proliferation and invasiveness via upregulating FOXP4 expression by sponging miR-4316, *Archives of biochemistry and biophysics* 653 (2018) 63-70.
- [148] W.B. Yin, M.G. Yan, X. Fang, J.J. Guo, W. Xiong, R.P. Zhang, Circulating circular RNA hsa_circ_0001785 acts as a diagnostic biomarker for breast cancer detection, *Clinica chimica acta; international journal of clinical chemistry* (2017).
- [149] R. He, P. Liu, X. Xie, Y. Zhou, Q. Liao, W. Xiong, X. Li, G. Li, Z. Zeng, H. Tang, circGFRA1 and GFRA1 act as ceRNAs in triple negative breast cancer by regulating miR-34a, *Journal of experimental & clinical cancer research : CR* 36(1) (2017) 145.
- [150] K. Zhang, S. Che, Z. Su, S. Zheng, H. Zhang, S. Yang, W. Li, J. Liu, CD90 promotes cell migration, viability and sphereforming ability of hepatocellular carcinoma cells, *International journal of molecular medicine* 41(2) (2018) 946-954.
- [151] L. Fu, T. Yao, Q. Chen, X. Mo, Y. Hu, J. Guo, Screening differential circular RNA expression profiles reveals hsa_circ_0004018 is associated with hepatocellular carcinoma, *Oncotarget* 8(35) (2017) 58405-58416.
- [152] X. Yang, Q. Xiong, Y. Wu, S. Li, F. Ge, Quantitative Proteomics Reveals the Regulatory Networks of Circular RNA CDR1as in Hepatocellular Carcinoma Cells, 16(10) (2017) 3891-3902.
- [153] X.Y. Huang, Z.L. Huang, Y.H. Xu, Q. Zheng, Z. Chen, W. Song, J. Zhou, Z.Y. Tang, X.Y. Huang, Comprehensive circular RNA profiling reveals the regulatory role of the circRNA-100338/miR-141-3p pathway in hepatitis B-related hepatocellular carcinoma, *Journal of proteome research* 7(1) (2017) 5428.
- [154] L. Yu, X. Gong, L. Sun, Q. Zhou, B. Lu, L. Zhu, The Circular RNA Cdr1as Act as an Oncogene in Hepatocellular Carcinoma through Targeting miR-7 Expression, *PloS one* 11(7) (2016) e0158347.
- [155] T. Yao, Q. Chen, Z. Shao, Z. Song, L. Fu, Circular RNA 0068669 as a new biomarker for hepatocellular carcinoma metastasis, (2018) e22572.
- [156] W. Jiang, D. Wen, L. Gong, Y. Wang, Z. Liu, F. Yin, Circular RNA hsa_circ_0000673 promotes hepatocellular carcinoma malignance by decreasing miR-767-3p targeting SET, *Journal of clinical laboratory analysis* 500(2) (2018) 211-216.

- [157] L. Zhong, Y. Wang, Y. Cheng, W. Wang, B. Lu, L. Zhu, Y. Ma, Circular RNA circC3P1 suppresses hepatocellular carcinoma growth and metastasis through miR-4641/PCK1 pathway, *Biochemical and biophysical research communications* 499(4) (2018) 1044-1049.
- [158] G. Chen, Y. Shi, M. Liu, J. Sun, circHIPK3 regulates cell proliferation and migration by sponging miR-124 and regulating AQP3 expression in hepatocellular carcinoma, *Cell death & disease* 9(2) (2018) 175.
- [159] J. Yu, Q.G. Xu, Z.G. Wang, Y. Yang, L. Zhang, J.Z. Ma, S.H. Sun, F. Yang, W.P. Zhou, Circular RNA cSMARCA5 inhibits growth and metastasis in hepatocellular carcinoma, *Journal of hepatology* 68(6) (2018) 1214-1227.
- [160] L. Fu, S. Wu, T. Yao, Q. Chen, Y. Xie, S. Ying, Z. Chen, B. Xiao, Y. Hu, Decreased expression of hsa_circ_0003570 in hepatocellular carcinoma and its clinical significance, *Journal of clinical laboratory analysis* 32(2) (2018).
- [161] L. Fu, Q. Chen, T. Yao, T. Li, S. Ying, Y. Hu, J. Guo, Hsa_circ_0005986 inhibits carcinogenesis by acting as a miR-129-5p sponge and is used as a novel biomarker for hepatocellular carcinoma, *Oncotarget* 8(27) (2017) 43878-43888.

Figure Legends

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram showing different pathways involved in circRNA biogenesis. (a) Intron-pairing driven circularization (exonic or exon-intronic formation). (b) Intron-pairing driven circularization (intronic formation). (c) Spliceosome dependent circularization. (d) RBP driven circularization.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of circRNA mechanisms to regulate gene expression in eukaryotes. (a) Sponge activity sequestering miRNAs or RBPs. (b) regulation of alternative splicing. (c) regulation of parental gene expression. (d) regulation of nuclear entry. (e) protein production.

Table 1. Biomarker studies of circRNA in cancer.

Tumour	Biomarker Type	circRNA	Source	Cohort size*	Method	Ref
Colorectal	Diagnostic	<i>hsa_circ_0126897</i>	T	4	MA	[108]
		<i>hsa_circ_001569</i>	T	30	RT	[71]
		<i>circ-BANP</i>	T	3	MA/RT	[109]
		<i>circ-ITCH</i>	T	45	RT	[82]
	Diagnostic and prognostic	<i>hsa_circ_0014717</i>	T	46	RT	[110]
		<i>hsa_circ_0000284</i>	T	178	RT	[111]
		<i>hsa_circ_001649</i>	T/S	64	RT	[112]
		<i>hsa_circ_0000567</i>	T/B (Exo)	102	RT	[113]
		<i>hsa_circ_000984</i>	T	76	RT	[114]
		<i>hsa_circ_0003906</i>	T	122	RT	[115]
		<i>hsa_circ_103809</i> , <i>hsa_circ_104700</i>	T	6	MA/RT	[116]
		<i>circCCDC66_10_8</i>	T	12	NGS/RT	[117]
		<i>ciRS-7</i>	T	153	RT	[78]
		<i>hsa_circ_0000069</i>	T	6	MA/RT	[118]
<i>hsa_circ_001988</i>	T	62	RT	[119]		
Lung	Diagnostic	<i>circFARSA</i>	T/P (Exo)	10	NGS/RT	[120]
		<i>hsa_circ_0001346</i>	T	50	RT	[121]
		<i>F-circEA</i>	T/P	11	RT	[122]
		<i>circRNA-FOXO3</i>	T	45	RT	[86]
		<i>hsa_circ_103595</i>	T	41	RT	[123]
		<i>hsa_circ_0012673</i>	T	33	RT	[124]
		<i>hsa_circ_0000064</i>	T	50	RT	[125]
		<i>circ-ITCH</i>	T	78	RT	[83]
	Diagnostic and prognostic	<i>circ-404833</i> , <i>circ-406483</i>	T	14	MA/RT	[98]
		<i>hsa_circRNA_103809</i>	T	44	RT	[126]
		<i>hsa_circ_0079530</i>	T	92	RT	[127]
		<i>circPRKC</i>	T	5	MA/RT	[128]
		<i>hsa_circ_0014130</i>	T	3	MA/RT	[129]
		<i>hsa_circ_0013958</i>	T/P	3	MA	[96]
Gastric	Diagnostic	<i>circ-ZFR</i>	T	48	RT	[130]
		<i>hsa_circ_0001136</i> , <i>hsa_circ_0000284</i> , <i>hsa_circ_0000211</i> , <i>hsa_circ_0004771</i> , <i>hsa_circ_0000524</i>	T	16	NGS	[131]
		<i>hsa_circ_0001017</i> , <i>hsa_circ_0061276</i>	T/P	6	MA	[132]
		<i>hsa_circ_0047905</i> , <i>hsa_circ_0138960</i> , <i>hsa_circRNA7690-15</i>	T	5	MA/RT	[133]
		<i>Circ-ITCH</i>	T	684	RT	[84]

	Diagnostic and prognostic	<i>hsa_circ_0000520</i>	T/P	5	MA/RT	[134]
		<i>hsa_circ_0000745</i>	T/P	20	RT	[135]
		<i>hsa_circ_0000181</i>	T/P	115	RT	[136]
		<i>circRNA_100269</i>	T	112	RT	[91]
		<i>hsa_circ_0003222</i>	T	80	FISH	[65]
		<i>circ_104916</i>	T	70	RT	[137]
		<i>hsa_circ_0006633</i>	T/P	96	RT	[138]
		<i>hsa_circ_0058246</i>	T	3	MA/RT	[139]
		<i>hsa_circ_0003159</i>	T	108	RT	[140]
		<i>ciRS-7</i>	T	102	RT	[79]
		<i>hsa_circ_0014717</i>	T	3	MA/RT	[141]
		<i>hsa_circ_0001895</i>	T	96	RT	[142]
		<i>hsa_circ_00001649</i>	T/S	76	RT	[143]
		<i>hsa_circ_0000190</i>	T/P	104	RT	[90]
		<i>hsa_circ_0000096</i>	T	101	RT	[144]
		<i>circPVT1</i>	T	3	NGS/RT	[88]
	<i>hsa_circ_002059</i>	T/P	101	RT	[89]	
		<i>circ-202308, circ-104423, circ-104916, circ-100269</i>	T	125	NGS/RT	[92]
Breast	Diagnostic	<i>circRNA-001175, circRNA-100438, circRNA-000911, circRNA-001283</i>	T	5	MA/RT	[145]
		<i>circ-FOXO3</i>	T	14	RT	[87]
		<i>hsa_circ_0008717</i>	T	4	MA/RT	[74]
		<i>circDENND4C</i>	T	30	RT	[76]
		<i>hsa_circ_103110, hsa_circ_104689, hsa_circ_104821, hsa_circ_006054, hsa_circ_100219, hsa_circ_406697</i>	T	4	MA/RT	[146]
	Diagnostic and prognostic	<i>circMYO9B</i>	T	41	RT	[147]
		<i>hsa_circ_0001785</i>	P	10	MA/RT	[148]
		<i>circGFRA1</i>	T	222	RT	[149]
Hepato-carcinoma	Diagnostic	<i>hsa_circ_0067531, hsa_circ_0057096</i>	T	8	RT	[150]
		<i>hsa_circ_0004018</i>	T	5	MA/RT	[151]
		<i>CDRIas</i>	T	41	TMA	[152]
		<i>hsa_circRNA_100338</i>	T	4	MA/RT	[153]
		<i>circMTO1</i>	T	7	MA/RT	[66]
		<i>circZKSCAN1</i>	T	102	RT	[68]
		<i>CDRIas</i>	T	35	RT	[154]
		<i>hsa_circ_0005075</i>	T	3	MA/RT	[93]
	Diagnostic and	<i>hsa_circ_0001649</i>	T	89	RT	[94]
		<i>hsa_circ_103561</i>	T	100	RT	[155]
	<i>hsa_circ_0000673</i>	T	51	RT	[156]	

	prognostic	<i>circC3PI</i>	T	47	MA/RT	[157]
		<i>hsa circ 0000284</i>	T	50	RT	[158]
		<i>hsa circ 0001445</i>	T	5	MA/RT	[159]
		<i>circ-ITCH</i>	T	288	NGS/RT	[85]
		<i>hsa circ 0003570</i>	T	107	RT	[160]
		<i>hsa circ 0005986</i>	T	81	RT	[161]
		<i>ciRS-7</i>	T	108	RT	[81]

*Number of patients enrolled in the identification, or in the validation in case there is no an identification approach. T; tissue, B; (whole) blood, S; serum, P; plasma, (exo); exosome. RT; qRT-PCR, MA; microarray, NGS; next generation sequencing (RNAseq).